

PRINCIPLES AND METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE SKILLS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Turdieva Mokhira Jurakulovna

Bukhara State University,

Lecturer of the preschool education department.

mohira.turdiyeva@bk.ru

Abstract: *This article describes the results of scientific research and opinions about the types of educational principles in the development of creative abilities of preschool children, the components of teaching creative activities, the stages of development of creative abilities.*

Key words: *creative ability, creativity, preschool education, pupil, integration, pedagogy, development, principle, creativity.*

When a child is born and grows, it is important to create physical, social and psychological opportunities for communication, learning and development in the social environment. The knowledge of preschool children about the world develops and improves from opportunities created at the right time, which is of great importance for the development of society. Such conditions are created in preschool educational organizations, where regular educational activities with children continue, which is the basis for the development of abilities.

Solving the problem posed in our research on the development of creative abilities of preschool children demanded the development of a model for the development of creative abilities based on a person-oriented and innovative approach.

In developing the pedagogical model for developing creative abilities of preschool children based on a person-oriented and innovative approach, we followed the following principles:

The principle of self-expression. Each pupil has a need to demonstrate his intellectual, communicative, artistic and physical abilities. It is very important to encourage and support his desire to show and develop his natural and social abilities.

The principle of individuality. Creating conditions for the individual formation of the pupil's personality is the main task of the preschool education organization. It is necessary not only to take into account the individual characteristics of the student, but also to contribute to his future development in every way.

The principle of subjectivity. Individuality is characteristic only of people who have subjective powers and skillfully use them to build activities, communication and relationships. It is necessary to contribute to the formation and enrichment of the student 's personal experience, becoming a real subject in the life of the group.

Selection principle. Without selection, it is impossible to develop individual characteristics and subjectivity of the student , to show his abilities. Pedagogically, it is desirable for the student to live and be educated in conditions with subjective powers in choosing the goal, content, forms and methods of organizing the educational process . It is for this purpose that preschool groups have an open developmental environment (developmental centers).

The principle of activity, creativity and success . The principle of encouraging the student to succeed is considered. This is the inclusion of active life views of the student in the game. It is extremely important for the pupil to be maximally oriented towards creativity in his game and productive activities, and to have experience in his own creative activities. Individual and collective creative activity allows to identify and develop its individual characteristics.

The principle of trust and support . It is important to enrich pedagogical activities with humanitarian, person-oriented education and training technologies. Trust, self-awareness, and self-encouragement should be supported, and excessive demands and excessive control should not be imposed. Internal motivation, not external influences, determines the success of education .

The principle of a different approach. Solves the tasks of effective pedagogical assistance in improving the personality of the students, helps to create special pedagogical situations that help to open the psycho-physiological, personal abilities and opportunities of the students. It is development depending on the nature, health, mental and physical structure, abilities and inclinations and perception of the student.

The created pedagogical model is considered a social order, and based on the individual-oriented and innovative approach of the "First Step" State curriculum, the methodology for developing the creative abilities of preschool children (**the structure of the developed model presented in the picture**) consists of improvement and includes the following :

– targeted component – implementation of strategies aimed at developing the creativity of students in innovative ways consists of a complex of pedagogical and innovative conditions. In this, the innovative approaches of the pedagogue focused on the student's personality were implemented:

- creativity qualities of pedagogues;
- motivation to educate students' creativity;

- to cultivate creativity and mental sharpness;
- in the creation of creative products was realized.

Approaches focused on the educated person include the following in the set of completed pedagogical works:

- communicative approach;
- intellectual flexibility approach;

- an approach to finding exclusive solutions to didactic problems. The content component, which includes such things, reveals the main directions and content of the activity.

An integrated component of teaching creative activity - reveals the main directions and content of its activities. The content of educational and educational activities using the previously listed innovative technologies is aimed at developing the creative abilities of preschool children, which is one of the main conditions for creating a creative environment, because only in creativity there is a change in activity that determines the self-development of all subjects of the educational process . .

The development of creative abilities of preschool children is carried out in the following stages:

the organizational and practical stage (stages, conditions, forms , methods) includes activities that ensure the process of developing the creative abilities of middle and older preschool children.

- ***initial stage*** (creating favorable conditions for the development of creative abilities under the conditions of using innovative technologies, general goals are formed at this stage, motivation and work options are offered for the joint activity of educators and pedagogues of the preschool educational organization .

- ***process stage (implies the organization of the activities*** of all subjects of the educational environment, i.e. the student , pedagogue , parents) for the development of creative abilities of middle-aged and older children under the conditions of using this or that technology . According to him, the pedagogue - educator should act in the following directions according to the stages of work : goal setting, process planning, process implementation, work reflection, correction. At this stage, there is a step-by-step development of the creative abilities of preschoolers , taking into account the level of their formation.

Assessment monitoring component activity by the educator and student reveals the effectiveness of the content of pedagogical work .

The productive stage (includes the analysis of the results of the development of the creative abilities of the students, the monitoring of the development of preschool

children is carried out, the level of development of the indicators of creative abilities is determined). Step by step creative abilities in the process of educational activity

It should be completed by setting the development goal, searching for a single motivation, choosing and evaluating the quality of the work performed.

- the *result stage* (includes the analysis of the results of the development of creative abilities of preschoolers, note in the observation notebook the level of development of the components of creative abilities, for example, flexibility of thinking, fluency and originality).

This analysis component has its own quality indicator elements and the pupil has the following conditions: passion for creative activity, formation of interest, mastery, development, improvement, and stabilization.

preschool children is a complex of educational support elements. In the process of educational activity, the gradual development of creative abilities should be completed with the determination of levels, the search and selection of a single motivation, and the analysis of the quality of the work performed.

In conclusion, the topic of creative abilities at present shows the relevance and necessity of organizing educational activities for the development of creative abilities in preschool educational institutions.

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